

OPTIMIZATION OF AIR VOLUME IN WATER HAMMER: PUMP SHUTDOWN IN SINGLE-CHARACTERISTIC PIPELINE

Miloud LAHBARI^{1*}, Saddek HEZIL²

¹ *Laboratory of Studies of Industrial Energy Systems, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2 – Mostefa Ben Boulaïd Batna 05000, Algeria*

² *Department of Hydraulics, Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2 – Batna 05000, Algeria*

*Corresponding author Email: m.lahbari@univ-batna2.dz

ABSTRACT: Protection against water hammer, a common phenomenon in water pumping stations and hydroelectric power stations, requires the installation of appropriate equipment to mitigate over- and under-pressures resulting from sudden or accidental pump operation (instantaneous stops or starts) that can cause pipes to burst or flatten. In this article, an air reservoir is proposed as a solution to limit these pressures to levels compatible with the strength of the materials. The solution of the governing equations corresponding to this phenomenon was obtained by the characteristic method, which gave an optimal air volume of 4.5 m³, in perfect agreement with the volume obtained by Bergeron's graphical method from an initial volume of 3.0 m³. The pressure in the discharge pipe drops to -32.59 m at the end of the first phase, then reaches 66.59 m in the fourteenth phase before stabilizing at 60 m. The recommended standard capacity for this air tank is approximately 6 m³, considering a water volume representing 32% of the air volume.

KEYWORDS: Water Hammer, air tank, over-, under-pressure, air volume, pressure wave, phase.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this study is to size the air reservoir (water hammer arrester), which is a necessary and appropriate piece of equipment for limiting to acceptable values both the overpressure and the under pressure resulting respectively from a sudden start-up or shutdown of a pump (Figure 1).

These pressures can arise during the operation of networks, both in hydroelectric systems and in pumping stations, since the role of these facilities is to respond to instantaneous maneuvers and, consequently, to transient flow regimes.

These flow regimes can create pressure loads (overpressures and depressions) that can exceed the load-bearing capacity of the material or fall below the admissible value in relation to the natural ground level for laying a pipe at a minimum depth, which must be above the minimum curve of the envelopes of the depressions. These overpressures and depressions can cause the pipe to burst or flatten, respectively.

This equipment consists of limiting the size of these pressure loads, both over- and under- pressures, to values compatible with the strength of the pipes and ensuring that the compressibility of the liquid and the deformation of the pipes walls are reversible,

in order to avoid any permanent deformation or breakage of the installed hydraulic installations.

To achieve this, the necessary capacity of the tank must be forecast, and the following methods of resolution are mainly available:

- Bergeron's graphic method
- Simplified methods.

The first makes it possible to solve all the problems associated with this phenomenon, even the most complex ones, so that it has become an indispensable aid for design engineers in engineering offices. This method takes into account the elasticity of the pipe material and the compressibility of the liquid.

The other methods are those used in special cases and in which the movement of the liquid is considered to be mass movement, since only the compressibility of the liquid is taken into account and the wall of the pipe, in this case, is considered to be perfectly rigid and non-deformable.

Until now, the graphical method has been used to determine air tank capacity, although it is laborious. With the advent of computers and their increasing power, this method has been replaced by the numerical method (Dupont., 1981), which will make it possible to deal with much more complex phenomena in order to improve accuracy and optimize calculation time.

Fig.1 Calculation diagram

1.1 Purpose of the research

The aim of this research is not only to determine numerically the capacity of the air reservoir to protect the equipment in the pumping station and the discharge pipe against the water hammer phenomenon (Nashat et al. 2013), but also to find the optimum air volume (W), which must protect and limit both over- and under-pressure to acceptable values in relation to the limit values required by the material. This volume of air is determined as a function of time and on the basis of a series of air volumes (W_0), which are chosen initially at the start of the calculations, the latter should lead to a result of a series of maximum air volumes (W_i), determined at different phases (θ_i) and, among which, a single optimal volume (W_{max}), can be observed at a well-defined time. This volume will then be recorded after comparison with other maximum volumes determined in a similar way. By comparing these maximum volumes, it is possible to identify a minimum volume which is optimal from an economic point of view and which meets the requirements mentioned above.

1.2 Choice of the used method

The flow of water is governed by the equations of dynamics and continuity. These partial differential equations are hyperbolic in nature and can be transformed into total differential equations and integrated along curves known as the characteristic curves (Nitescu and Constantin 2010). This numerical method converges better than other methods, so it was used in this case, knowing that this

problem can be solved explicitly or implicitly (Nițescu et al. 2011).

This method is applied to a pumping station, delivering into a single-characteristic delivery pipe, and for which air tank equipment is required to protect ancillary hydraulic equipment and structures.

The values obtained by Bergeron's graphical method (Shamloo et al., 2009) for a given initial volume W_0 of 3m^3 were used to compare and validate the results obtained by the characteristics method.

The analysis was carried out using the characteristics method, which has permitted, on the one hand, to understand how this volume of air reacts and varies as a function of time (Abuaziah et al., 2013) and in relation to each volume of air initially chosen at the start of the calculations and, on the other hand, to identify an optimum volume from among the various maximum determined volumes.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology adopted the following steps:

2.1 Calculation assumptions

The study of the volume of the air tank is based essentially (according to the diagram in Figure 1) on the following assumptions:

- This is a single-characteristic drive.
- Stopping the pump is considered instantaneous.
- The flap valve, located in front of the pump, is assumed to close abruptly as soon as the pump stops and to remain constantly in its vertical position throughout the transient process, its closing time

being less than the time taken for the flow to reverse towards the flap valve.

- The height (h_r) of the bumper in relation to the axis of the pipe will not be taken into account as it is lower than the pressures and geometric height ($h_r \ll H_g$).

- The variation in the volume of air ΔW , in the air tank, is neglected in relation to the initial volume W_0 .

- The static load (h_s) in relation to the water level in the air balloon and the water tank is considered invariable and equal to the geometric height (H_g) in relation to the axis of the pipe and the plane of the water tank.

- The pressure in the storage tank in steady state is taken to be equal to the absolute pressure of the pump in steady state, given that the pump is located close to the air tank.

- The inertia in the pipe connecting the air tank to the discharge pipe is negligible, which can be explained by the fact that the flow in this pipe is considered to be a mass movement.

- The mean flow velocity is negligible compared with the wave propagation velocity ($V \ll a$)

- The plane of the tank remains constant throughout the water hammer phenomenon.

2.2 Calculus data

- $a=1045\text{m/s}$
- $d=0.5\text{m}$
- $d_1=0.25\text{m}$
- $d_2=0.13\text{m}$
- $Q=0.37\text{m}^3/\text{s}$
- $\gamma=1.4$
- $\lambda=0.02761833$
- $L=1000\text{m}$
- $H_g=50\text{m}$

The initial air volume values are chosen as follows:

$W_0 = \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.25, 3.5, 3.75, 4.0, 4.5 \text{ and } 5.0 \text{ m}^3\}$

It should be noted that this example has been treated using Bergeron's graphical method with an initial volume of 3m^3 , where the pressure losses are concentrated in a single point at the beginning of the discharge pipe (Shamloo et al., 2009).

2.3 Air tank operating principle

The volume of air compressed and maintained at a pressure H_t (at time t) in the steady state, initially arbitrarily chosen W_0 at the base of this volume of air, a sufficient quantity of water, under the same pressure as in the tank.

This quantity will be used, when the pump stops instantaneously, at time $(t+\Delta t)$, to transform the pressure energy into a flow energy which will be propelled to the base of the water hammer arrester and through the nozzle connected to the discharge pipe. This flow expelled from the tank having the role of compensating for the water deficit and thus limiting the depressions which may appear along the discharge pipe and also serving to maintain the head of the pipe and to combat any under-vacuum (pressure drop) along the discharge pipe.

It will also cause a lowering of the water level in the air reservoir, which will subsequently cause an expansion of the volume of air which is observed by the expansion of the volume of air ($W_0+\Delta W$), this expansion of the volume can be explained, by the presence of the pressure drop (ΔH) recorded in the tank, in a lapse of time Δt , the absolute pressure which was initially in the initial state H_t will assume its final state and, at the instant $(t+\Delta t)$, a value equal to:

$$H_{t+\Delta t} = H_t + \Delta H \quad (1)$$

The equation governing this variation in pressure from an initial to a final state, in relation to the quantity of air pressurized in the tank, can be presented by the following polytropic gas equation:

$$H_t W_t^\gamma = H_{t+\Delta t} W_{t+\Delta t}^\gamma = C \quad (2)$$

$$W_{t+\Delta t} = W_t + \Delta W$$

$W_{t+\Delta t}$: Volume of air at absolute pressure $H_{t+\Delta t}$ at time $t=(t_0 + \Delta t)$ under transient conditions.

W_t : Volume of air at absolute pressure H_t at the initial instant in steady state.

Since the pressure inside the volume of air is considered to be equal to the absolute pressure at the height of the water column, if we assume at time $(t+\Delta t)$ that the flow rate is equal to the absolute pressure at the height of the water column, this flow rate will be equal to the absolute pressure at the height of the water column.

This flow ($Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M^3}$) leaving the tank, the purpose of which is to compensate for the water deficit in the discharge pipe during this transitional regime, will generate a variation in pressure (H_t to $H_{t+\Delta t}$), as well as a variation in volume (W_t to $W_{t+\Delta t}$) at the base of the water hammer and at the junction point (M), connecting the nozzle to the discharge pipe, where we consider the three points M^1 , M^2 et M^3 surrounding this point (M).

The indices on the letter M indicate the sections considered around this point, which are characterized at each instant by the same pressure value according to the principle of continuity of pressure at a point.

$$H_t^{M^1} = H_t^{M^2} = H_t^{M^3} \quad (3)$$

The flow rates at the junction of the three pipes upstream and downstream of the discharge pipe and

the pipe connecting the air tank must at all times satisfy the continuity equation (Boillat, and De Souza., 2004), the algebraic sum of the inflow and outflow rates of which must be equal to zero.

$$Q_t^{M3} + Q_t^{M1} - Q_t^{M2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Changes in flow Q^{M3} and pressure H^{M3} between instants t and $(t+\Delta t)$ (while considering a short period of time so that it can be assumed that the flow rate at the base of the anti-hammer valve Q^{M3} remains constantly) equal to a value of the average flow rate. The air expansion must take place with this same average flow rate:

$$Q_{moy}^{M3} = \frac{1}{2}(Q_t^{M3} + Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M3}) \quad (5)$$

Given a time $t+\Delta t$, the flow ($Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M1}$) delivered by the pump vanishes, since it is an instantaneous shutdown, the flow rates at the base of the water hammer and downstream of the junction point will become identical, thus the average flow rate can also be written as follows:

$$Q_{moy}^{M2} = \frac{1}{2}(Q_t^{M2} + Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M2}) \quad (6)$$

When the pump stops, this maneuver changes the steady state to a transient state.

The steady state will last for half a phase, as long as the reservoir is not reached by the positive wave, which starts as soon as it is generated, at the moment the pump stops instantaneously, either voluntarily or accidentally.

Once the wave reaches the reservoir, it remains there and is reflected in the opposite direction to the positive flow, reaching the pump again at a time equal to one phase θ , in front of which there is a non-return valve that remains closed in its vertical position during the transient state.

If a nozzle is fitted at the base of the water hammer arrester to reduce excess pressure by creating head losses in the opposite direction to the flow, in order to convert pressure energy into velocity energy in the event of water falling, the diaphragm incorporated in the pipe acts as a Broda nozzle with a contraction coefficient equal to $\frac{1}{2}$.

The time it takes for the wave to travel a distance equal to one round trip from the discharge pipe will be equal to one phase.

$$\theta = \frac{2L}{a} \quad (7)$$

To simplify calculations, the phase was taken equal to one unit of measurement ($\theta = 1$ unit).

The time taken for the wave to reach the tank is equal to half a phase ($\frac{1}{2}\theta$) and if we consider a period of time equal to half a phase ($\Delta t = L/a = \frac{1}{2}$ of the unit), this time for which a variation in volume can be observed can be determined by the following relationship:

$$\Delta W = \frac{1}{2}(Q_{t-\Delta t}^{M2} + Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M2})\Delta t \quad (8)$$

Equation (2) at time $t = 0.5$ and $\Delta t = 0.5$ can be written as follows:

$$H_{t+\Delta t}^{M4} = \frac{C}{\left\{W_{t-\Delta t}^{M4} + \frac{(Q_{t-\Delta t}^{M2} + Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M2})\Delta t}{2}\right\}^{\gamma}} \quad (9)$$

Neglecting the height of the air tank h_r in relation to the axis of the discharge pipe:

$$H_S \approx H_g = \text{Constant} \quad (10)$$

The pressure in the pipe at the point H_t^{M3} will be equal to the geometric height in absolute value becomes: $H_t^{M3} \approx H_g + 10$

As for the pressure inside the tank, taking into account the local pressure drop Δh_t in the nozzle will be:

$$H_t^{M4} = H_t^{M3} + \Delta h_t \quad (11)$$

The pressure in the storage tank under steady-state conditions is taken to be equal to the head of the pump, since the pump is located close to this protective equipment.

$$H_0^{M4} = H_t^{M4} + h_0^L \quad (12)$$

$$H_0^{M4} (W_0^{M4})^K = C \quad (13)$$

h_0^L : Linear head loss in the discharge pipe at steady state.

$H_0^{M4} W_0^{M4}$: Pressure and volume of air inside the air tank and at the limit of the water surface ($M_0^4 - M_0^4$) in figure (1), being steady state at time $t=0$.

2.4 Determination of the variables (H_1^{M2} , Q_1^{M2}) located at the limit of the connection point between the main pipe and the air tank

For the two transient variables at time $t=\theta=1$ and point $M(H_1^{M2}, Q_1^{M2})$, a system of two equations must be established:

- The first equation is that of the compatibility equation valid along the CM negative characteristic line (Chaudhry., 1986 and Tam., 2009) in the (t,x) plane, firstly, the length of the pipe is positively oriented from the origin of the coordinates and that it extends over a length (L) , along the axis (x) , as for the coordinate (t) represents the time for which the two variables must be determined at the instant $t=2L/a$, this time is that required for the propagation wave starting from the reservoir at a time equal to half a phase to arrive at the point M, located at the section M^2 belonging to the main pipe.

$$H_{t+\Delta t}^{M2} - H_t^R - B(Q_{t+\Delta t}^{M2} - Q_t^R) - rQ_t^R |Q_t^R| = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$B = \frac{a}{gS} \quad (15)$$

- The second equation governs the absolute pressure of the compressed air in the balloon, which is determined in relation to the law of variations in pressure and volume of compressed air put under

pressure according to the evolution of the law of perfect gases.

Equation (9) at time $t=0.5$ and $\Delta t=0.5$, can be written as:

$$H_1^{M4} = \frac{C}{\left\{ W_0^{M2} + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right\}^\gamma} \quad (16)$$

2.5 Boundary conditions

Given that the water level in the water reservoir is constant (figure 1) throughout the transient regime and that the flow rate at the foot of the reservoir and at the end of the discharge pipe will not be disturbed until this reservoir is reached by this positive wave, this is why the initial and boundary conditions at the level of this reservoir, for all the points in the pipe where the passage time of the positive wave is less than or equal to half a phase ($t=0.5$), at these points the flow rate will be equal to the initial flow rate (figure 2), but the pressure must be equal to the steady-state gauge pressure less the corresponding linear pressure drops, with the exception of the pressure at the reservoir, which is always equal to the absolute geometric head.

$$H_{0.5}^R = H_0^R \text{ And } Q_{0.5}^R = Q_0^R \quad (17)$$

By replacing these initial conditions, the compatibility equation takes the following form:

$$H_1^{M2} - H_0^R - B(Q_1^{M2} - Q_0^R) - rQ_0^R | Q_0^R | = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$H_1^{M2} - BQ_1^{M2} = H_0^R - BQ_0^R + rQ_0^R | Q_0^R | \quad (19)$$

$$H_1^{M2} = CM + BQ_1^{M2} \quad (20)$$

$$CM = H_0^R - BQ_0^R + rQ_0^R | Q_0^R | \quad (21)$$

Fig. 2 Representation of the positive (CP) and negative (CM) characteristic lines in the (t, x) plane

Taking account of local pressure losses in the nozzle

When the depression at point M^3 at time $t=1$, H_1^{M3} will be equal to:

$$H_1^{M3} = H_1^{M4} - \Delta h_1 \quad (22)$$

Δh_1 : Local pressure drop in the nozzle under non-steady-state conditions when the wave travels a distance equal to one phase, then at this instant the pressure at the point M_1^{M2} at the beginning of the discharge pipe will be equal to:

$$H_1^{M2} = H_1^{M4} - \Delta h_1 \quad (23)$$

The positive flow direction is the same as the positive flow direction and if $Q_1^{M2} > 0$, it comes:

$$m_1 = \frac{(0.92d_2)^2}{d_1^2} \text{ and } cd_1 = f(m_1) \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta h_1 = \frac{cd_1 k_1^2}{2gs^2} (Q_1^{M2})^2 = \beta (Q_1^{M2})^2 \quad (25)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{2d^2}{(0.92d_2)^2} \quad (26)$$

$$\text{If } Q_1^{M2} < 0, m_2 = \frac{0.5d_2^2}{d_1^2} \text{ and } cd_2 = f(m_2) \quad (27)$$

$$\Delta h_1 = \frac{cd_2 k_2^2}{2gs^2} (Q_1^{M2})^2 = \beta (Q_1^{M2})^2 \quad (28)$$

$$k_2 = \frac{2d^2}{d_2^2} \quad (29)$$

Based on the principle of pressure continuity at the connection point, the equations can be equated:

$$H_1^{M3} = H_1^{M2} \quad (30)$$

$$H_1^{M2} = H_1^{M4} - \Delta h_1 = CM + BQ_1^{M2} \quad (31)$$

$$H_1^{M4} = CM + BQ_1^{M2} + \Delta h_1 = CM + BQ_1^{M2} + \beta (Q_1^{M2})^2 \quad (32)$$

$$H_1^{M4} = \frac{C}{\left\{ W_0^{M3} + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right\}^\gamma} = CM + BQ_1^{M2} + \beta (Q_1^{M2})^2 \quad (33)$$

If we put $x = Q_1^{M2}$ the previous equation can be rearranged as follows:

$$F(x) = \frac{C}{\left\{ W_0^{M3} + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right\}^\gamma} - CM - BQ_1^{M2} - \beta (Q_1^{M2})^2 = 0 \quad (34)$$

The function $F(x)=0$ is a non-linear equation that can be solved using Newton's iterative method, whose solution is written as follows:

$$x^{n+1} = x^n - \frac{F(x^n)}{F'(x^n)} \quad (35)$$

x^{n+1} : Estimate of order n+1

x^n : Estimated order n

$F'(x)$: Derivative of the function $F(x)$

$$F'(x) = \frac{\gamma C \Delta t}{2 \left[W_0 + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right]^\gamma} + \left\{ \left[W_0 + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right]^\gamma \right\} \{ B + 2\beta Q_1^{M2} \} \quad (36)$$

$$U_1 = \left[W_0 + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right]^\gamma \quad (37)$$

$$U = \left[W_0 + \frac{(Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2})\Delta t}{2} \right]^\gamma \quad (38)$$

$$C_3 = B + 2\beta Q_1^{M2} \quad (39)$$

$$F'(x) = \frac{\gamma C \Delta t}{2U_1} + UC_3 \quad (40)$$

$$Q_1^{M2(n+1)} = Q_1^{M2(n)} - \frac{F(x)}{F'(x)} \quad (41)$$

$$\left| Q_1^{M2(n+1)} - Q_1^{M2(n)} \right| \leq \varepsilon \quad (42)$$

Once the flow rate (Q_1^{M2}) has been determined at time $t=1$ at point M^2 , it will first be used to calculate the variation in air volume, which is determined by

the average flow rate leaving the duct corresponding to a variation in time Δt .

Variation in air volume:

$$\Delta W_1^4 = \left(\frac{Q_0^{M2} + Q_1^{M2}}{2} \right) \Delta t \quad (43)$$

The volume of air back in the air tank at the time equal to one phase will be equal to:

$$W_1^4 = W_0^4 + \Delta W_1^4 \quad (44)$$

The absolute pressure inside the air tank for the same time as before will be equal:

$$H_1^{M4} = \frac{C}{U} \quad (45)$$

The absolute pressure inside the pipe with linear head loss:

$$H_1^{M2} = H_1^{M4} - \Delta h_1 \quad (46)$$

$$H_1^{M2'} = H_0^R + B(Q_1^{M2} - Q_0^R) \quad (47)$$

$$H_1^{M2} = H_1^{M2'} + h_{L0}^{M2} \quad (48)$$

The absolute pressure inside the pipe without linear pressure drop:

$$H_1^{M2'} = H_1^{M4} - \Delta h_1^{M2} - h_{L1}^{M2} \quad (49)$$

The effective pressure remaining inside the pipe with pressure drop:

$$H_1^{M2} = H_1^{M2'} - 10 \quad (50)$$

$$V_1^{M2} = \frac{Q_1^{M2}}{S} \quad (51)$$

$$V_{moy}^{M2} = \frac{(V_0^{M2} + V_1^{M2})}{2} \quad (52)$$

2.6 Calculation diagram for points on the pipe boundary conditions

The pressure versus time variable on the left boundary (figure.3) will be determined from the initial conditions in the reservoir of the characteristic for CM^- at time $t=0.5$ (Deng et al., 2013).

Fig.3 Boundary conditions on the left (point M^2) and right (Reservoir)

On the curve $W_{max}=f(W_0)$ in figure (4), we can see that the optimum corresponds to an initial volume of $2m^3$ giving a maximum volume of W_{max} of $4.26m^3$.

On the other hand, volumes between $2.5m^3$ and $3m^3$ give maximum volumes of $4.31m^3$ and $4.5m^3$ respectively.

Fig. 4 Variation in maximum volume as a function of initial volume

The curves show $H_d=f(W_0, \theta)$ and $H_{ef}=f(W_0, \theta)$ (figure 5), volumes of less than $2m^3$ are to be excluded from the choice of initial volume, since they give negative pressures in the pipe when the pump is stopped during the first phase (1□). On the other hand, volumes greater than $3m^3$ are also to be eliminated from the choice, because volumes greater than $3m^3$ give pressures well above the required standards, which is why the range that remains to be studied favorably is the one belonging to this range including $[2-3m^3]$.

Fig.5 Variation in maximum vacuum and remaining effective pressure in the pipe

On the curve $W_0=f(M^3, \theta)$ curve (figure 6), we can see that volumes with a value greater than or equal to $3.75m^3$ have the same 3θ depression phase. On the other hand, the volumes in the range $[2.0-3.0m^3]$ corresponding respectively to phases of 6θ and 4θ are located in a favorable zone, while the volumes in the range $[0.5-1.5m^3]$ have the same phase equal to 7θ and belong to the unfavorable zone for the reason given above.

Initial volumes corresponding to a value of three vacuum phases (3θ) are to be excluded, since these volumes result in oversizing of the air tank, which

may have a financial impact on the supply and installation of this equipment, and all volumes corresponding to seven vacuum phases (7θ) are to be eliminated, since the latter result in negative pressures in the pipe when the pump stops instantaneously during the first phase (1θ). Given that the completion of the four-phase depression phase (4θ) is better than the completion of the six-phase depression phase (6θ), and taking into account the safety measures to limit any timely depressions that may occur along the pipe, the choice of $3.0m^3$ as the optimum initial volume for the remainder of this study has been adopted. The curve shows $H_d=f(M^2, \theta)$ of the effective pressure remaining in the pipe during the absolute depressions at the time of maximum expansion of the volume of air, corresponding to the volumes of ($2.0, 2.5$ and $3.0m^3$) are respectively ($17.11, 17.97$ and $20.45m$) or in effective pressure remaining in the discharge pipe ($7.11, 7.97$ and $10.45m$), these pressures are respectively observed during the depression phases (6θ), (5θ) and (4θ), the favorable remaining pressure in the pipe must be greater than or equal to $10m$, which is why the optimum volume is that of $3.0m^3$ corresponding to a remaining pressure of $10.45m$.

The absolute depressions in the pipe during the first phase (1θ) corresponding to volumes of ($2.0, 2.5$ and $3.0m^3$) are respectively ($13.50, 25.45$ and $34.03m$), or in effective pressure ($3.5, 15.45$ and $24.0m$).

For safety reasons, the remaining pressure in the pipe must be greater than $10.0m$, as the vacuum phase for the $3.0m^3$ volume is achieved in $4\theta < 5\theta < 6\theta$ and this with the aim, so that the air tank intervenes in a suitable time in order to limit, possibly, the dangerous depressions to acceptable values, from where the optimal choice is $3.0m^3$.

The curve shows $H_s=f(M^2, W_0)$ (figure 6), of the variation of the overpressures according to the initial volume which are higher than $3.0m^3$ are insignificant, because, these last corresponding generate important volumes, as for the volumes which are lower than $2.0m^3$ will not be taken into consideration, as these generate negative pressure values during the first phase. The volumes remaining in the favorable zone are those in the interval $[2.0-3.0m^3]$, as it was previously decided that the optimum volume is that of $3.0m^3$ which corresponds to an overpressure of $66.59m$ observed during the period frequency of (14θ). On the curve $\theta=f(M^2, w_0)$ the overpressures for the volumes between 2.0 and $3.5m^3$ have the same overpressure phases (14θ) (figure 7), but their depressions are different because for the volume $2.5m^3$, the depression phase is (5θ) and for the volumes: 3.0 and $3.5m^3$, they have the

same phase (4θ) (figure 6).

Fig.6 Variation in initial volume with θ

Fig.7 Variation of overpressure phase as a function of initial volume

Fig.8 Variation of the remaining effective overpressure in the pipe in relation to the geometric height as a function of the initial volume

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When the pump stops instantaneously, it should be noted that the pressure curves (Figure 9) in the air tank $H=f\{v(M^4, t)\}$ and in the pipe with and without pressure losses, which are respectively $H_{1,2}=f\{v(M^2, t)\}$

These pressures are calculated for an initially chosen air volume of 3.0m^3 , these absolute pressures in the tank and in the pipe are respectively a function of the velocity in the nozzle and in the discharge pipe due to the volume of water propelled from the air tank, this volume serving to make up for the water deficit in the pipe and to maintain its head in order to limit, if necessary, the dangerous depressions which may arise along the pipe, this quantity of water of 0.64m^3 , initially expelled from the tank and observed over a period of time equal to a phase θ , will give a maximum flow speed in the nozzle of 26.05m/s , which will in turn generate a lowering of the volume of air and a drop in pressure in the balloon, at the start of the transient regime and, which takes on a value of 53.37m .

Fig. 9 Pressure variation in storage tank, pipe with and without pressure drop $H = .f\{v(M, t)\}$

It can be seen that the maximum depression corresponding to a velocity of 1.71m/s at the beginning of the pipe at an absolute pressure of 32.59m with pressure losses and 26.0m with no pressure drop, these pressures decrease as the average speed decreases progressively in the direction of positive flow, until it becomes equal to zero. This is the phase of maximum expansion in the air tank with a maximum volume of 4.5m^3 and a minimum pressure of 39.69m , equal at this moment to that at the beginning of the pipe.

Once the flow velocity becomes negative in the opposite direction to the positive flow and decreases to reach a maximum value in absolute terms of 0.60m/s , which corresponds to a pressure of 48.37m in the balloon, this velocity continues to decrease until it is cancelled again to give rise to a maximum overpressure in the balloon during phase (14θ) corresponding to an overpressure equal to 66.59m which balances with that of the pipe which corresponds to a volume of air of 3.11m^3 .

Once the pump stops, the curve shows $H_d = H_d(M_2, t)$ (figure 10), the absolute maximum depression appears at the time of the first phase (1θ)

of the transitory regime which corresponds to a value equal to 32.59m , on the other hand, the absolute overpressure would occur when the number of the overpressure phase reaches the phase (14θ) and which has for value 66.59m , thanks to this equipment, the pressures attenuate and weaken, at which point, and after a certain number of phase indefinitely, the oscillations and amplitudes of pressure disappear and become practically equal to a constant, equal to the geometric height in absolute value (60m) and that the flow regime re-establishes itself in steady state.

Fig. 10 Variation in pressure $H = H(M^2, \theta)$ at the start of the line with head loss

On the curve $W = f(M^3, \square)$ (figure 11), the maximum volume of air reaches 4.5m^3 at the end of phase (4θ) , this is the phase of maximum expansion and during maximum overpressure this volume becomes equal to 3.11m^3 at the end of (14θ) which corresponds to 66.59m , the damping of amplitudes can be observed as a function of time with oscillations that take place between 3.3m^3 in overpressure and 3.4m^3 in expansion.

Fig. 11 Variation in air volume $W = f(M^3, \theta)$

The largest value of the air volume differential can be seen on the curve $dW = f(M^3, \square)$ curve in figure (12), during the first phase and which corresponds to

0.64m³, this is generated by the negative pressure which occurs during this phase and which causes a negative pressure equal to 32.59m.

Fig. 12 Differential of air volume variation as a function of phase $dW=f(M, \theta)$

On the curve $H=f(M^3, \square)$ (figure 13), the variation in the quantity of water of 0.64m³, will cause a loss of head through the nozzle of the order of 20.76m, this value is maximum in the positive direction of flow and decreases in the opposite direction of flow, then increases to reach a second peak but with a different value equal to 12.4m, these peaks attenuate as a function of time and become practically zero.

Fig. 13 Variation of local pressure drop in the nozzle as a function of phase $dh=f(M^3, t)$

On the curves in figure (14), $H_d=f(M^4, \theta)$ and $h=f(M^3, \square)$, it can be seen that the pressure in the storage tank increases with the pressure drops in the opposite direction to the positive flow and decreases in the opposite case. Once the pressure drops become practically zero, the pressure in the storage tank becomes equal to the static pressure in absolute value.

Fig. 14 Variation in absolute pressure in the air tank and local pressure drop

Fig. 15 Variation in velocity at the start of the discharge pipe as a function of phase $V=f(M^2, \theta)$

Fig. 16 Graphical determination of the maximum volume corresponding to the minimum pressure

Fig. 17 Comparison between experimental values (A. Dupont 1981 [5]) and calculated values obtained by the characteristics method

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The right choice of initial air volume leads to an optimum economic volume based on the following principles:

Firstly, by giving a series of initial volumes in order to deduce maximum volumes for each given initial volume and this in order to establish a curve $W_{\max}=f(w_0, \square)$ curve, which allows us to highlight the optimum volume to be observed on this curve and which must verify and fulfill all the conditions required by the pressures of the pipe material to be protected.

Knowing the geometrical characteristics of the pipe, we can draw two curves, the first being the maximum depression $H_d=H_d(W_0, \theta)$ and the second the remaining effective pressure $H_{ef}=H_{ef}(W_0, \theta)$ in the pipe, both of which are a function of the variation in initial volume and time in units of phases; these pressures are those which arise during the first phase. From these two curves, and after examining them, we can exclude volumes which may generate negative depressions and those whose overpressures are insignificant.

Secondly, after the systematic elimination of inadmissible values, the favorable interval for analysis and comparison of the results to be studied must be limited.

Thirdly, we plot the curve $W_0=f(M^3, \theta)$ in order to find the volume in which the negative pressure phase is minimal and which must comply with the permissible negative pressure conditions. Next, we can also plot the negative pressure curve as a function of the phase at the point belonging to the discharge pipe $H_d=H_d(M^2, \theta)$, these curves allow us to deduce the optimum volume for which the negative pressure phase is minimal θ_{\min} . The negative pressure during this phase is 39.55m.

Similarly, we can plot the overpressure curve as a function of phase $H_s=H_s(M^2W_0)$, on which the overpressure phase is observed during (14□) corresponding to the optimum volume of 3.0m³ and giving an overpressure of 66.59m, it is necessary at the same time to plot the phase curve as a function of the chosen initial volume $\square=\square(M_2, W_0)$, in order to show the large volumes whose pressure variations become insignificant and to highlight the overpressure phase corresponding to the optimum volume chosen (14□).

A validation was established after the study and examination of the results determined by the method of the characteristics, one notes that the results obtained are identical to those determined by the graphic method known as of Bergeron described in pages [274-275] of reference (Shamloo et al., 2009) as well as the same graph illustrating pressures as a function of time, in the pipe was determined and then compared with that on page 290, entitled: recording of pressures observed during water hammer events, using a recording manometer supposedly installed at the start of the pump on the discharge pipe. On this record sheet, we can see that there was a depression during the first phase θ de with a value equal to 32.59m, and that an overpressure appeared during the 14 θ phase with a value equal to 66.59m, i.e. a pressure in relation to the absolute static pressure of 6.59m. Beyond this value, the pressure begins to decrease until it reaches the absolute static pressure of 60m, at which point the flow regime becomes permanent and stable.

5 REFERENCES

- A., Dupont., 1981. *Hydraulique Urbaine*. Editions Eyrolles Paris.
- A., A., Nashat et al. 2013. Analysis of Different Protection Methods Against Water Hammer on Water Supply Network. *Journal of Engineering Sciences*, Vol. 41, No. 6.
- C., S., Nitescu, A., Constantin., 2010. Systematic Hydraulic Study for the Preliminary Sizing of the Surge Tanks Mounted Close to the Pumping Station, *Wseas Transactions on Systems*, Vol. 9, (10).
- C., S., Nițescu et al. 2011. Hydraulic Study on Pumping Stations Equipped With Air Chamber Mounted Next to the Pump. *International Journal of Mathematical Models and Methods in Applied Sciences*, Vol. 5, No. 8.
- H., Shamloo et al., 2009. Leak Detection in Pipelines by Inverse Backward Transient Analysis, *Journal of Hydraulic Research*; Vol. 47, No. 3, 311-318.
- I., Abuaziah et al., 2013. Modeling and Controlling Flow Transient in Pipeline Systems: Applied for Reservoir and Pump Systems Combined

with Simple Surge Tank. Rev. Mar. Sci. Agron. Vet. 3.

J., L., Boillat, P., De Souza., 2004. Hydraulic System: Modélisation des Systèmes Hydrauliques a Ecoulements Transitoires en Charge, Communications du Laboratoire de Constructions Hydrauliques, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne. Suisse.

M., H., Chaudhry., 1986. Applied Hydraulic Transient, Second Edition, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company Inc (Eds), New York.

N., D., Tam., 2009. Fluid Transients in Complex Systems with Air Entrainment, Thesis Submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Mechanical Engineering Department. National University of Singapore.

T., Deng et al., 2013. Hydraulic Transients Induced by Pigging Operation in Pipeline with a Long Slope, Journal of Applied Mathematics. [Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1155/2013/231260](http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1155/2013/231260).

6 NOTATION

The following symbols are used in this paper:

- a : Wave propagation speed [m/s].
- d : Diameter of the pipe [m].
- d_1 : Diameter of the tube [m].
- d_2 : Diameter of the nozzle [m].
- e : Thickness of the pipe [m].
- H_g : Geometric height [m].
- L : Length of the discharge pipe [m].
- Q : Flow rate delivered into the pipe [m^3/s].
- S : Cross-section of the pipe [m^2].
- W : Volume of air [m^3].
- W_0 : Initial volume of air [m^3].
- γ : Polytropic coefficient.
- λ : Coefficient of head loss resistance.